

SIMULATION OF OXIDATION IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Novel modeling strategies were developed in order to reduce the computational effort required to simulate oxidation in textile composites. The oxidation behavior in heterogeneous configurations was found to be complex and dependent on a number of factors. A hybrid model for analyzing textile composites was validated and used to simulate the oxidation behavior in a graphite/PMR-15 plain weave composite.

Keywords: oxidation, finite element analysis, textile composites, homogenization, effective properties, diffusion, transient analysis, oxidation layer growth

INTRODUCTION

Composites are becoming popular in structures that operate in extreme environments, including high temperature applications in the aerospace industry. While optimal design through extensive experimental testing is not practical, computational analysis of these materials is not trivial either. The overall goal of this research effort is to use a finite element framework to analyze damage progression in textile composites due to the combined effects of oxidation under high temperature and mechanical loads.

Determining the effect of high temperature oxidation and aging on the mechanical behavior of composites is a very complex and challenging problem. There are a number of studies in the literature investigating the different time-dependent physical, chemical and mechanical damage mechanisms[1-4] as well as experimental characterization studies[5-10]. But there is still much more work that needs to be done in order to reliably predict the composite behavior using mechanistic approaches. The planned damage progression analysis involves performing an oxidation analysis that simulates the diffusion of oxygen into the composite and tracks how much the material has oxidized. This is a complex coupled problem with the oxidation affecting the mechanical stress in the material and the mechanical damage affecting the oxidation progression. A constitutive theory will be used to determine the amount of damage in terms of strength or stiffness degradation based on the oxidation state of the material in the composite. The damage will not affect the oxidation properties in the initial version.

The progressive damage analysis will track the damage state in the composite and calculate the stress state in the composite with respect to time as the oxidation progresses.

A precursor to the complete damage progression analysis is the oxidation analysis of the composite which is quite complex because in reality the fiber and matrix both have their own response to high temperature oxidation and aging. In addition, when the two are combined to form the composite, the anisotropic oxidative response is even more complex to simulate because of the fiber-matrix microstructure. Micro-cracks and damage formed at the interface between the fiber and matrix affect the oxidative response of the composite. Experimental work on unidirectional composites [11-13] and on textile composites[14] shows that when the specimens are allowed to oxidize through all its free surfaces, the composites are found to oxidize more rapidly along the fiber direction as compared to the transverse direction

The work presented in this paper is a continuation of the development of strategies for achieving the goal of simulating oxidation and damage progression in a textile composite. In previous work by the authors[15], effective oxidative properties were determined for the tows because it is not practical to discretely model the fibers in the textile composite. The work also described the formulation of the oxidation model used, which was adopted from the work by Pochiraju, Schoeppner and Tandon[16-18] who have used this model to simulate the oxidation of neat PMR-15 resin with reasonable accuracy compared to experimental observations. Varghese and Whitcomb [15] used the oxidation model to simulate oxidation in a square array of fibers. The strategies to determine effective oxidation properties for the microstructure were validated using three configurations and the results were found to be in good agreement with the corresponding discrete models. Although the fibers were assumed to be impermeable in those simulations, the homogenization procedure was developed without that constraint.

In this particular paper, the focus is on developing strategies to speed up the oxidation analysis in order to simulate the oxidation behavior in textile composites without needing excessive computational resources. The results of the simulation of oxidation in a plain weave graphite/PMR-15 composite will be presented. The next section will very briefly describe the model that is used to simulate the oxidation process.

OXIDATION MODEL

The oxidation process in a polymer such as PMR-15 resin, is a combination of the diffusion of oxygen and its consumption by reaction, which also results in the creation of by-products such as carbon dioxide. For the purposes of modeling the oxidation of polymers, the process is assumed to be dominated by the diffusion of oxygen into the polymer. The oxidation model that is used in this effort is primarily based on the work by Pochiraju et al[16-18], which uses the conservation of mass equation for diffusion (Fick's second law) modified by a term to model the rate of consumption of the diffusing oxygen during chemical reaction. The primary governing equation for the oxidation process, taking into account the need to model inhomogeneous materials, is given by

$$C^{\infty} \frac{\partial \bar{C}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} J_i + R = 0 \quad (1)$$

where \bar{C} is the normalized concentration of oxygen. The actual concentration in the material is given by

$$C = \bar{C}C^\infty \quad (2)$$

where C^∞ is the saturation concentration of the material. J_i is the flux and the relationship between flux and the concentration gradient is given by Fick's first law,

$$J_i = -C^\infty D_{ij} \frac{\partial \bar{C}}{\partial x_j} \quad (3)$$

and D_{ij} is the 2nd order diffusivity tensor. R is the reaction rate that, in general, would depend on the concentration of oxygen, temperature and the availability of un-oxidized polymer. As the oxygen reacts with the polymer, the amount of polymer available for oxidation depletes and the oxygen will continue to diffuse to the interior of the polymer to react. The amount of polymer available for oxidation is defined by an oxidation state variable called ϕ . The value of the oxidation state variable at which the polymer is considered to be completely oxidized with no more polymer available for reaction is defined as ϕ_{ox} . The oxidation state can be physically defined to be the ratio of the current weight of the material over its original un-oxidized weight. Therefore, the oxidation state has a range from 1 to ϕ_{ox} where an oxidation state value of 1 denotes the un-oxidized polymer. An oxidation state value between ϕ_{ox} and 1 indicates that the material is partly oxidized and can still undergo more oxidation. To illustrate this, three zones were defined by Pochiraju et al[16-18] as shown in Figure 1. Consider that the left end of the idealized material shown in the figure is exposed to oxygen and the oxidation propagates to the right. Zone III is the region of the material that is un-oxidized with an oxidation state of 1 and as the oxidation continues, this zone becomes smaller while Zone I which denotes the fully oxidized material with an oxidation state of ϕ_{ox} increases. The zone in between where the oxidation state is between ϕ_{ox} and 1 is called the active zone and is denoted by Zone II.

Figure 1: Oxidation zones and corresponding values of the oxidation state variable

When $\phi = \phi_{ox}$ at a material point, R reduces to zero and the process simplifies to just diffusion at that point. An issue that arises when analyzing oxidation in heterogeneous materials is that although the oxidation state value for any material has an upper limit of 1, its lower limit for different materials is not necessarily the same. This makes it inconvenient to make comparisons as to how much oxidation has taken place. For example, the same oxidation state value for two different materials need not imply that

they are equally close to being fully oxidized or that they have the same amount of material left to oxidize. In order to make this comparison easier, a new variable is introduced called the oxidation level denoted by Φ . The oxidation level variable linearly scales the oxidation state variable so that all materials have an oxidation level that ranges from 0 to 1. This relation is given by,

$$\Phi = \frac{\phi - \phi_{ox}}{1 - \phi_{ox}} \quad (4)$$

The governing equations described above result in nonlinear transient behavior, which is implemented in a finite element program. The effective oxidation properties for a microstructure such as a unidirectional laminate or a tow are obtained by using homogenization techniques described in Ref [15].

For a more detailed description of the governing equations, the derivation of the finite element formulation and the homogenization strategy, refer to Ref [15].

STRATEGIES TO SPEED UP THE ANALYSIS

The oxidation analysis is inherently more computation intensive than a simple diffusion analysis because of the complex governing equations. The oxidation state variable needs to be calculated for each integration point in the mesh at every time step. The oxidation model appears to require a more refined mesh and a smaller time step size compared to a corresponding diffusion model. This makes it even more important to explore methods to speed up the oxidation analysis without losing required accuracy. This section describes three approaches to expedite the analysis: optimized model parameters, adaptive meshing, and a hybrid strategy developed specifically for analyzing textile composites.

Optimization of model parameters

Depending on the material properties and other values in the finite element formulas, there are limits to the element size and time step size beyond which meaningless results are obtained. In addition to the basic approximation for the time integrations, there are several approximations made in the finite element formulation [15] to handle the nonlinearity in the governing equations. The accuracy of these approximations depends on parameters such as the time step size as well. Parametric studies were conducted to determine the optimized parameters for the materials that would be analyzed in this work. The study found that the maximum element size was 4 microns. Similarly, the maximum initial time step size was determined to be 0.3 minutes. In general, the optimal time step size need not be constant throughout the simulation because of the nonlinear oxidation behavior. This means that the time step size can potentially be ramped up or down during the simulation so as to maintain the optimal time step size. It was found that after the initial 40 hours of oxidation simulation, the time step size could be increased to 5 minutes without any significant effect on the oxidation layer growth behavior. This considerable increase in the time-step size is related to a change in one of the parameters in the constitutive model that occurs after 40 hours of simulation.

Adaptive Mesh Strategy

Even with the optimizations, the analysis is computation intensive and a new strategy was developed to speed up the analysis. The strategy exploits certain characteristics of

the oxidation behavior which allows the size of the analysis region to be modified as the simulation is underway. To explain how this strategy works, the oxidation behavior in PMR-15 resin needs to be described first. For this purpose, oxidation of a simple configuration is considered. The simple configuration is a block of neat resin that is exposed to oxygen on one pair of opposite surfaces that are 40 mm apart and protected from oxygen on the other surfaces. This configuration can be analyzed using a 1-D model. Moreover, taking advantage of symmetry, only half of the block needs to be modeled. Table 1 gives the material properties used to model the neat PMR-15 resin. For a complete description of the different oxidation material properties, refer to Ref [15].

Diffusivity	
D_{unox}	$53.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2/\text{min}$
D_{ox}	$78.22 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2/\text{min}$
R_0	$3.5 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^3 \text{ min})$
ϕ_{ox}	0.187
C^∞	$0.79 \text{ mol}/\text{m}^3$
α	$0.01 - 0.0067(t/40) : t < 40$ $0.0033 : t > 40$ (t in hours)
$f(C)$	$\frac{2\beta C}{1 + \beta C} \left[1 - \frac{\beta C}{2(1 + \beta C)} \right]$
β	0.919

Table 1: Oxidation material properties for the neat PMR-15 resin

An important part of the analysis is post-processing the results of the simulation to provide a measure of the oxidation behavior. The oxidation behavior is visualized in terms of the growth of the oxidation layer. The oxidation layer initiates from the surfaces exposed to the oxygen and grows into the interior as the material becomes oxidized. Although ideally the material is said to have started oxidizing when the oxidation level drops below 1, the oxidation layer thickness is defined by the point at which the oxidation level, Φ , dips below 0.99, indicating that 1% of the oxidizable material has oxidized. Therefore, an element is assumed to have started oxidizing if the oxidation level at each of the material integration points falls below 0.99. If the oxidation state is above 0.99, the element is assumed to be un-oxidized and if it is below 0.01 it is assumed to be fully oxidized. A post-processing routine was written that calculated the growth of the oxidation layer in the 1D model. This involved extrapolating the oxidation state values from the integration points to the nodal points, averaging the extrapolated values at a node if the node shared elements of the same material and solving for the location in the model where the oxidation level value met the specified upper and lower limits. This routine was also generalized to work for 2-D and 3-D models. Note that the prescribed upper and lower limits of 0.99 and 0.01 respectively are valid only for a completely oxidizable material such as neat resin. When dealing with homogenized material such as a tow, the entire material does not oxidize because the fibers are assumed to be inert and therefore the prescribed limits will be different. This will be discussed in more detail in the results section of this paper.

Figure 2 shows the predicted oxidation layer growth for the block of neat resin over a period of 200 hours. It can be seen that the resin oxidizes very quickly in the initial 20 hours or so and then gradually slows down to where the oxidation layer grows almost linearly. The difference between oxidation and diffusion-only is that for oxidation, the oxygen molecules do not diffuse as quickly because they are consumed in oxidizing the material. Thus, the reaction term in the governing equations gives the effect of a 'moving barrier' that allows almost no oxygen to cross over to the other side of the active zone until there is a sufficient level of oxidation within the active zone. This is evident by looking at the concentration profiles across the model at different snapshots during the simulation. Figure 3 shows the concentration profiles in the model at $t=2.5$ hrs, 50 hrs and 100 hrs. It can be seen that all the profiles have a similar shape. The profiles drop almost linearly from the exposed edge up to the 'moving barrier' and the concentration is practically zero for the rest of the model. The difference in each profile is that as time passes, the location of the 'moving barrier' shifts in the direction of the oxygen flow. This movement of the barrier is very slow compared to the diffusion-only process. This is illustrated in Figure 3 by the concentration profile of the corresponding

Figure 2: Predicted oxidation layer growth in neat PMR-15 resin

Figure 3: Concentration profiles for oxidation and diffusion models

diffusion model at 15 minutes. It shows that with only 15 minutes of diffusion, the oxygen concentration at every point in the model has already surpassed that of the oxidation model at 2.5 hours. Even after 100 hours of oxidation, the oxygen concentration is still practically zero past 0.06 mm whereas the corresponding concentration from the diffusion model after 15 minutes is more than 0.025 at 0.06 mm. This also explains why there is a close to linear drop of the concentration from the exposed edge to the 'moving barrier'. In each snapshot of concentration profile in the oxidation process, the region to the left of the moving barrier can be considered as a diffusion only region with fixed concentration boundary conditions – the specified concentration at the exposed boundary and zero concentration at the location of the barrier. Since the barrier is moving very slowly, the concentration profiles at the various time steps look very similar to that for the corresponding diffusion-only problem at steady-state, which is a nearly linear variation of the concentration.

The fact that the concentration of oxygen in the un-oxidized region of the material is practically zero can be exploited to speed up the analysis by constraining the degrees of freedom(dof) in most of the un-oxidized region to zero. This can lead to a considerable reduction in the number of unknowns, especially in the initial period of oxidation because most of the material is un-oxidized at that time. The challenge is in determining which regions of the material should be constrained and developing an efficient algorithm so that this can be automated. The regions very close to the active zone should not be constrained since the active zone is slowly moving to the interior of the material with each time step and that can affect the solution. Also, the regions should not be permanently constrained because that implies that those regions will never get oxidized, which is not the case.

Based on these requirements, the following algorithm was developed to automatically determine the regions to be constrained. A very small concentration value close to zero is chosen, say C^0 , in order to determine which regions are to be constrained. If the concentration at a node is more than C^0 , then that location is assumed to be inside the oxidation layer or close to it and therefore the dof for that node is left unconstrained. On the other hand, if the concentration at a node is less than C^0 , then the node is assumed to be in the un-oxidized region and far enough from the active zone, therefore that dof is constrained. This check is not performed at every time step. Instead, the check is performed every 15 or 20 time steps or some optimal number of time steps (say, N) chosen depending on the rate the active zone is moving. Therefore, once a check is performed, the constrained dofs remain constrained for the subsequent time steps until the time step right before the next check. In this time step preceding the check, all the artificial constraints are removed and the full system of equations is solved. This allows a minute amount of oxygen to enter the previously constrained region. In the next time step, the check is performed, at which time some of the previously constrained dofs will be unconstrained because the oxygen concentration has increased by a small amount. This cycle is repeated throughout the simulation. This strategy speeds up the analysis by a large factor because in the standard analysis, every time step involves solution of the entire system of equations whereas in the adaptive mesh analysis, the entire system of equations is solved only every N time steps. During the other time steps, the system of equations solved is much smaller. The check to determine the region to be constrained is also performed only every N time steps and the computation effort used for the check is miniscule compared to the savings obtained by solving a smaller set of equations. In

addition to those savings, whenever the check is performed and a region of the unoxidized material is constrained, the corresponding elements are also deactivated thereby speeding up the finite element assembly process as well. Parametric studies were performed by varying the two parameters, C^0 and N on 1-, 2- and 3-D models and it was found that the computation time could be reduced by 60-70%. For the work presented in this paper, C^0 was chosen to be 0.0001 mol/m^3 and N was chosen to be 20 time steps.

Hybrid Model

Conventional oxidation analysis of textile composites would require a full 3-D model. Given the length scales involved and the limitations on the element size, the mesh would require a huge number of elements. This would make the analysis very time-consuming in spite of the savings achieved by the adaptive mesh strategy. Moreover, considering that the overall goal of this research effort is to couple the oxidation analysis with the damage progression analysis, the combination would be prohibitively expensive. In an effort to make this more feasible, a hybrid analysis was developed to make the oxidation analysis more efficient.

The strategy applies to composite laminates that are exposed to oxygen from the top or bottom (or both) surfaces, but not the lateral edges. The strategy is illustrated in Figure 4. The hybrid analysis takes a three-dimensional model and divides it up into individual analysis domains in the in-plane dimensions as shown in Figure 4. The strategy

Figure 4: Schematic of hybrid model for analyzing textile composites

assumes that because of the boundary conditions applied on the model, the oxidation behavior will be such that the neighboring domains do not have an effect on each other, essentially assuming that oxygen does not flow from one domain to another. Therefore, the individual domains can be analyzed separately. Each individual domain is a three dimensional heterogeneous analysis region with curved material boundaries because of the undulation of the tows in the textile composite. The model assumes that the change in the diffusivity due to the undulation is not significant because the rotation angles in actual composites are relatively small. The analysis also assumes that the undulations of the tows are not significant enough to cause an impact on the oxidation behavior and this has been validated. Therefore, the domain can be converted into an equivalent domain with straight horizontal material boundaries based on the volume fraction of the different constituents in domain. Since the new equivalent domain has no inclined

material boundaries, it can be analyzed with a simple 1-D model. Thus, the 3-D model shown in Figure 4 can be replaced by an array of 64 1-D models, thereby reducing analysis time significantly. The hybrid model is implemented in the finite element analysis package in such a way that the input to the model is the same as the conventional 3-D model. Additional pre-processing work is not required and the array of 1-D models is automatically generated and analyzed without the need for human interaction. Moreover, the 1-D models can be run in parallel on multi-core processors, thereby increasing the efficiency even further. In order to validate this model for the material systems considered in this work, a number of configurations were analyzed. Due to limits on the length of this paper, only one of the configurations will be described in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will describe one of the configurations that was used to validate the hybrid model. This will be followed by a discussion of the results of the oxidation simulation of a plain weave textile composite.

A simple 2-D heterogeneous configuration with two materials was chosen where the material boundary is straight but at an angle to the horizontal edge as shown in Figure 5(a). The bottom edge is assumed to be exposed to oxygen whereas the other three edges are assumed to be impermeable. The configuration has the dimensions 200 microns x 100 microns. The material in the lower region is assumed to be neat PMR-15 resin and the other material is assumed to be a graphite/PMR-15 tow with a fiber fraction of 55.6%. The material properties of the resin and the formulas for obtaining the homogenized tow properties can be obtained from Ref[15]. The region is first divided into two domains and converted into equivalent 1-D models as shown in Figure 5(b). To compare the oxidation layer growth predicted by the 1-D models with the behavior in the actual 2-D model, the oxidation layer growths along different

Figure 5: 2-D configuration for validating hybrid model

vertical lines (numbered in Figure 5(a)) in the 2-D model are compared. Figure 6(a) plots the oxidation growth given by the equivalent 1-D domain 1 model along with that along lines 1, 3 and 5. It shows that the 1-D result agrees very closely with that of line 3 and not so much with that of lines 1 and 5, which are on the extreme edges of domain 1. Similar trends are seen in Figure 6(b), which shows corresponding plots for domain 2. Now the domains are further subdivided into domains 1-1, 1-2, 2-1 and 2-2 as shown in Figure 5(c). Due to lack of space, only the plots for domain 1-1 and 2-2 are shown in Figure 6(c) and (d). As expected, these results show that the equivalent 1-D domain models perform better at simulating the oxidation layer growth when the domain size is reduced.

Figure 6: Comparison of the oxidation layer growth from the different 1D models with the growth in the 2D configuration

One interesting behavior that was noticed during the validation was that when simulating oxidation of a heterogeneous model with neat matrix and tow, the predicted oxidation growth seems counter-intuitive when compared to that of a model with neat matrix alone. Consider the equivalent 1-D configuration for domain 1 in Figure 7 which is a heterogeneous model with neat resin and homogenized tow. Figure 8 compares the predicted oxidation layer growth for the configuration in Figure 7 with that of a pure resin model. One would intuitively expect that since the model with the tow is assumed to have inert and impermeable fibers, this would slow down the oxidation layer growth compared to a neat resin model that has no fibers. But Figure 8 shows that the model with the resin and tow has a faster oxidation layer growth. On further investigation, it

Figure 7: Equivalent 1D configuration for domain 1

Figure 8: Comparison of oxidation layer growth in the domain 1 (resin/tow) model and neat resin model

was seen that a number of factors influence this behavior. The tow in the model acts like a pseudo-barrier allowing the resin to saturate with oxygen much faster than the tow. Until the oxidation front reaches the vicinity of the material boundary, both the models behave in the same manner because the tow has no effect on the matrix that is being oxidized ahead of it. But once the tow begins to oxidize as well, the interface conditions regulate the flow of oxygen from the matrix into the tow and free oxygen starts to build up in the matrix. This is evidenced in Figure 9 which shows the oxygen concentration profile in the model at 100 hours. Figure 9 shows that the resin region in the resin/tow model (from 0 to 0.06 mm) has more oxygen than the same region in the neat resin model. The oxygen in the tow region (from 0.06 to 0.1 mm) is also more than that in the same region for the neat resin model. This could be due to a combination of factors. First, note that at 100 hours, the oxidation front has crossed the material boundary but is not too far from it. The material boundary is at 0.06mm and the oxidation front at 100 hours can be considered to be around 0.08mm, beyond which the oxygen concentration is practically zero. Secondly, the tow has less amount of resin that can be oxidized and therefore the maximum reaction rate is also less than that of the neat resin. That also means that the region consumes less oxygen (for oxidation) than the neat resin. Since the reaction rate in the tow is less than that in the neat resin and the oxidation front is fairly close to the material boundary, the tow region between the material boundary and the oxidation front also starts accumulating more oxygen than the corresponding region in the neat resin. Figure 10 gives the amount of free oxygen in the model throughout the

Figure 9: Comparison of concentration profile in the resin/tow model and neat resin model at 100 hours

Figure 10: Comparison of amount of free oxygen in the resin/tow model and neat resin model

simulation. It shows that until about 60 hours, the resin/tow model and the neat resin model have the same amount of free oxygen, but after 60 hours the resin/tow model builds up more oxygen in its material. This is not to be confused with the amount of oxygen consumed in oxidizing the polymer in the resin and tow regions. The neat resin model is expected to consume more oxygen than the resin/tow model because it has more material that can be oxidized and this is shown in Figure 11. Once the oxygen starts to build up in the matrix, it becomes fully oxidized more quickly and all the incoming oxygen is directed into the tow region, which is then used up to oxidize the polymer in the tow. Also note that an oxidation level of 0.99 at a material point in the neat resin region indicates that 1% of the resin in the material has oxidized. On the other hand, saying that 1% of the resin in a material point in the tow region has oxidized equates to an oxidation level of $(1 - 0.01(\text{matrix volume fraction}))$, which for this model is 0.99556. Figure 12 shows the oxidation level profile in the model at 10 hours. The

Figure 11: Comparison of amount of oxygen consumed in the resin/tow model and neat resin model

Figure 12: Comparison of oxidation level (Φ) profile in the resin/tow model and neat resin model at 100 hours

inset plot in Figure 12 shows a close up of the oxidation state of the two models between 0.08 and 0.095 mm. It shows that the oxidation level in the resin/tow model dips below 0.99556 at about 0.085 mm (at location A) whereas in the neat resin model, it dips below 0.99 at about 0.077mm (at location B). Overall, this oxidation behavior in the resin/tow model is due to a combination of factors such as the effective oxidation properties of the tow as well as the diffusion behavior in heterogeneous models and the relatively slow movement of the oxidation front into the interior of the material. Due to these factors, it is also seen that the location of the material boundary has an impact on the oxidation behavior but due to lack of space, it cannot be discussed in this paper.

The hybrid model was used to simulate the oxidation behavior in a symmetric two-ply graphite/PMR-15 plain weave laminate. Both the top and bottom surfaces are exposed

to oxygen. The composite is chosen to have a waviness ratio of 1/3. A full unit cell of the configuration is shown in Figure 13(a). By exploiting symmetry, it is possible to analyze the configuration using only 1/8th of the full unit cell as shown in Figure 13(b) with a transparent matrix. The hybrid modeling technique is used on the reduced domain, which is automatically subdivided into an array of 64 1-D model as described in the previous section. Since both the warp and fill tows have the same oxidation material properties and the effects of the undulation are assumed to be insignificant, the four quadrants in Figure 13(b) are essentially identical, therefore the results from the

Figure 13: Configuration and analysis domains for simulating oxidation in plain weave composite

corresponding 1-D models in the different quadrants will be the same. Additionally, within one quadrant (i.e. 1/32nd of the unit cell), based on the same assumptions of ignoring the effects of undulation, the region is symmetric about the plane as shown in Figure 13(c). Therefore, the only unique results from the analysis are those from the 10 domains numbered in Figure 13(d). Figure 14 gives the predicted oxidation layer growth for the 10 domains. It shows that there is considerable variation in the oxidation layer growth behavior of the 10 domains. At the end of 200 hours of oxidation, the thickest layer is 0.11 mm (in Domain 9) which is only slightly larger than half the thickness of a single ply. Figure 13(c) shows that domain 10 has the largest amount of matrix with a very small region of tow in the middle whereas domain 1 has the largest amount of tow with a very small region of matrix at the two ends. Although domain 10 has the largest amount of matrix, it is not the domain that has the thickest oxidation layer. This is because, as discussed earlier, in heterogeneous models the oxidation behavior is not very straightforward and depends on a number of factors such as the location of the material boundaries and the oxidation properties of each of the constituent materials. In each of the ten unique 1-D domains representing the weave microstructure, the material boundaries are at a different distance away from the exposed surface. This results in a varied oxidation behavior from the 1-D models. Since domain 10 is almost all resin with a small region of tow in the middle, its oxidation behavior would be expected to be close to that of a neat resin. Similarly, since domain 1 is almost all tow with a small regions of matrix at the two ends, its oxidation behavior would be expected to be close to that of a homogenized tow model. However, as explained earlier with the heterogeneous configuration, the behavior is not always close to that of the corresponding homogeneous model. Figure 15 shows the layer growth for

Figure 14: Oxidation layer growth in the 10 unique domains

Figure 15: Comparison of oxidation layer growth in domains 1 and 10 with that of a neat resin model and homogenized tow model

domains 1 and 10 as well as for a neat resin model and a homogenized tow model. It shows that domain 10 follows the same behavior as a neat resin model but once the oxidation front reach the tow material, domain 10 has a slightly faster oxidation layer growth. For domain 1, the oxidation layer is only slightly thicker than that in an all tow model. Due to space constraints, the behavior of all the domains cannot be discussed in detail in this paper. However, the analysis does show that the oxidation front does not

advance uniformly throughout the composite and the tow architecture plays a significant role in the variation.

CONCLUSION

Two novel strategies were developed to expedite the oxidation analysis of textile composites. The adaptive mesh strategy was found to reduce the computation time by 60-70%. The hybrid model made it possible to simulate oxidation in a textile composite within a practical timeframe. The hybrid model was validated using a 2-D configuration. The oxidation behavior in heterogeneous configurations was found to be complex and dependant on a number of factors. This behavior was investigated for a 2-D configuration consisting of neat resin and homogenized tow. The hybrid model was then used to predict the oxidation behavior in a plain weave composite. It was found that the microstructure and the effective oxidation properties play a significant role in how the oxidation front advances into the interior of the composite. The strategies described in this paper provide a practical and efficient method to simulate the oxidation behavior in textile composites. In future work, the oxidation analysis will be coupled with a damage progression analysis to predict the mechanical behavior under oxidation.

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